

Learning gains through reflection: The critical role of reflection in remote teaching and learning

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Abstract – *This study attempted to explore the experiences of the students, their issues and concerns during remote teaching and learning. This study used qualitative approach using critical analysis of the reflective essay. It used a four-step reflection process by York-Barr, et. al (2006). The reflective results of the student experiences during lockdown suggested several themes. These themes drawn from the personal experiences could the framework to their learning gains given the challenges at hand: a) appreciation of the school learning environment/physical interaction; b) challenges of teachers as perceived by students; c) academic efforts experiences; d) mental and body wellness challenge; e) transforming challenges to opportunities; and f) technological and home infrastructure challenge. These themes depicted the students' experiences, motivation, and learning gains during remote teaching and learning. Implications include that teachers can capitalize on the benefits of improved metacognition by implementing activities and interventions that allow students to reflect on their intellectual and motivational approaches to the situation.*

Keywords: Reflection, learning gains, metacognition.

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Introduction

There is a wide acceptance that reflection is as effective as a tool for enhancing learning and a relevant platform for improving metacognition. Moreover, it is mostly accepted that for addressing a real-world problem through intervention, as well as the research aim of contributing to knowledge (Avison et al., 1999; Baskerville & Myers, 2004; Coghlan & Brannick, 2005; Coskun, 2018; Davison et al., 2004). This resulted to Davison et al. (2004) in which developing a number of principles and assessment criteria include “the principle of learning through reflection” to discuss ongoing concerns with rigor (cited by Costello, 2008).

Student reflection is considered a potent authentic assessment of experiences, issues and concerns in life as a student. In this time of lockdown brought on by COVID-19, students were asked to reflect on their experiences, issues and concerns in teaching and learning remotely and how they intend to use the experiences in the future. By examining their reflection essay, the teacher could hear their voices and may provide more ideas and imperatives to “what else can done” during lockdown and when teaching and learning are facilitated remotely and what could be their possible advocacies. This study attempted to explore the experiences of the students, their issues and concerns during remote teaching and learning.

Two research questions are premised to answer the learning gains of the students after more than a year of studying remotely. The main issues that are needed to be addressed in this study are the student's descriptions to the remote delivery of teaching and learning and their plans in the future ensuing that experience. These two questions are based on the notion that we can explore their thoughts in this kind of extraordinary situation. As what Stynes et al. (2018) mentioned, the need to gain access to their thoughts and perceptions in order to understand their own social reality appears to be a valid consideration. It is premised that using reflection approach we can look into ways to enhance students' overall sense of personal empowerment in their abilities, as well as how to make things easier for them to think about their efforts from an academic, technological, and affective perspective. In this study, it is not the goal to make general statements about what students learn from reflection or how they perceive the activity. What the students were thinking, feeling, and planning for their future are what the researcher wanted to determine.

While reflection can be considered as a form of self-evaluation, the focus of this study was not on students' ability to evaluate their own work. Rather, students were asked to reflect on their experiences during remote delivery of teaching and learning. Thus, the articles that follow do not focus on reflection as a means of self-evaluation, but rather on reflection as a tool for improving metacognitive processes in order to boost overall motivation, identify learning gains, and perhaps, academic strategies.

Methodology

This study used qualitative approach using critical analysis of the reflective essay. It used a four-step reflection process by York-Barr, et al. (2006). The essay was analyzed using a four-process by Barr, et al. (2006). These are: Objective, Reflective, Interpretive and Decisional. Using the four-step process, the study applied using these processes: From the reflection instrument, student response data were classified according to themes.

A four-step reflection process was used to examine the reflection essays of the students. It consists of description (what happened); analysis and interpretation (why); overall meaning and application (so what); and the implication for action (now what). In the analysis, the statements indicators were identified as to positive, negative, and new realizations. The third process identified statement indicators which are categorized and formed into themes. The final process examined how the students made use and integrate those experiences in their future plans. Patterns were used to create themes in the second research question.

Descriptive coding was also used in the data analysis. Glesne (2016) writes that “*Data analysis involves organizing what you have seen, heard, and read so that you can make sense of what you have learned. Working with data, you describe, create explanations, pose hypotheses, develop theories, and link your story to others stories*” (p. 130). For organizational and analytical purposes, we used descriptive coding to identify patterns and themes that are being developed from the patterns.

Results

In this study, the aim is not to generalize about what students learn from reflection, or how they experience the practice. Instead, a specific set of student reflections, as well as student comments on those reflections, were described, which occurred at a specified time and location in answer to specific questions.

The objective of the essay is to describe the students' experiences during the lockdown brought by the pandemic. The first part of the analysis is to describe some of the experiences of the students. Statements selected and analyzed are related to the research questions raised. This is followed by identifying the positive and negative experiences indicators. These indicators are cross analyzed for patterns to form the themes.

Using the 4-cycle reflective process of the analysis, students' experiences during more than a year lockdown, and remote delivery of teaching and learning were described. The data is generally categorized as personal positive or negative experience. Majority of the participants wrote powerful descriptions of their experiences.

Personal Experiences

All students described their experiences in a concrete manner that allowed one to imagine how the pandemic and lockdown decimated their goals, academic visions and expectations. Salient statements were chosen, which meet the research questions asked. The integration of reflection in the classroom, with Colley et al. (2012) calling it a "key pedagogical strategy is realistic sense of efficacy and motivation". Students have an opportunity to 'write it out' even when they do not like or agree with it (Colley et al., 2012; Cavilla, 2017). Consider the following statements:

- During COVID-19, it is sad. Most of us don't have the money to buy laptops or tablets immediately or at all, computers and even internet.
- Spending time with tutees really helps me, especially that I am the only one in my specialization, to conquer the feeling of loneliness and they also motivate me in doing my best.
- I was sad because the most awaited event in the school was postponed. I thought that it was just only one week that there are no classes.
- I already miss my friends and the school and the things that we made together.
- I just feel stress and anxiety because I always think about how can I manage to help in the house while studying.
- The other challenge for me is time management because I'm not just a student inside our house, I also help my uncle and aunt in doing the household chores, and a cousin who helps him to his study if he needs me.
- I feel sad and anxious, I am sad because I feel like my college years was cut short and wasn't able to enjoy my college life; also I thought I am able to see my classmates and my friends again and we were able to catch up.
- I am anxious because of my scholarship; I always think what if they cut off my scholarship because the fund for pandemic is lacking.
- There's plenty of realization during the pandemic. I am a returnee. I am already in my forties when I decided to study again. this whole online class setting is not good for my mental health, but of course with the help of my friend who is also a returnee, she always encourages me and told me not to give up on my dream.

- This pandemic that we are going through is not that easy. I myself was not prepared at all, what more my parents, my whole family but we are all trying to survive.
- There are no computer shops at all to be rented, and if you are going outside you need to present a quarantine pass so that you would be allowed to go out of your home. So, I was stuck again and I have to think another new way to do my thing.
- It affects me personally, since I cannot do the normal things I do; my daily routine was missing.
- At first, I was really sad and disappointed when this happened but now, I'm getting used to it, since I have no choice. I just need to bear with it. I believe that it affects the society more than it affects me.
- First month to third month of quarantine for me is a hell, but time passed by, I learned to fight with my depression. I learned to be productive even though it was quarantine.
- There was a time that I didn't do my activity for days, I was so stressed and my mind was so blank that I can't even think what to do. When I do my activities, I just stared at the monitor even if I'm just staring, I felt like crying. I lost my interest in studying, I wanted to stop because I felt lazy to study.
- I have experienced problems in my mental health, just to share that I have an anxiety or fear about sickness. I always exaggerate and over think the things that I feel like for example; if I feel heat in my body, I will think that I have fever and my mind will automatically think that I have symptoms of the virus.
- I experience finding my worth as a student and future teacher. I contemplate that, is it worth it if I'm going to enroll this semester even if it is virtual and distant learning? Am I going to meet my professors' standard and how am I going to learn? These are the questions that keeps on coming to my mind because I think it is a big risk if I'm going to enroll, and I will not be able to acquire new knowledge, and I think that I cannot cope with the changes and adjustments for the online class.
- I have encountered family pressure. They think that it is easier to learn in online class because we are just in our house, they don't know that it is harder for me because it is not my learning style, I acquire knowledge through social interaction.
- Discipline is a trait that I have truly tested and improved during distance learning. As a student at home, it was my responsibility to be mentally present at "school" even if I am at home. I had to make sure I'm waking up at the right time to prepare before classes, have time to learn with my peers and to work on my own, to submit my requirements, on top of doing my responsibilities as a family member.

Below are few statements in the analysis phase that indicate positive, negative and new realizations. The statements showed that majority have expressed negative thoughts about their lockdown experience due to pandemic. Apart from expressing few positive thoughts, most students attached new realizations from the positive disposition, or realizations for new opportunities to capitalize ensuing lockdown.

Table 1. Positive and Negative Indicators

Positive Indicators	Negative Indicators
This pandemic has a lot of positive effects on us. I noticed that this is the best time to be productive and that this time is given to us by God for a reason.	My family and I got into depression. Life goes on, were facing the pandemic in a new normal, following the rules of the government, like wearing face mask, face shield and practice social distancing.
This time can be used as a time for character development and growth.	Quarantine has a serious impact on mental health. I agree with that, because right now I experience anxiety, sadness maybe this is a depression.
I always maximize things that I have because I also learned that we should not take things for granted, we should always be contented on what we have and use it to its full potential.	I was an ordinary college student, going to school every day, meet my classmates, teachers, and friends, and because of Covid-19 pandemic, I was not able to go to school, I cannot meet my friends, classmates, and teachers. I feel so stress that time.
I believe that even the world stopped because of this lockdown the learning of each one of us continues.	My life changed when Covid-19 came in the Philippines. There are moments in my lives when I feel like giving up. Especially those times when enhanced community quarantine implemented.
I am not that healthy, but this lock down thought me to eat healthy and to took care of myself. I think I am in my better version today and I hope no one will destroy that version of me.	I am so afraid to think that all of my plans in life will never happen or it will never be the same again.
The first positive experience that I have encountered is the idea of being independent, because of this pandemic it teaches me to believe on the capabilities that I can do.	It's draining to feel that we're worrying about our grades when our country is facing healthcare and economic issues.
Education during the pandemic to tell you honestly, it is hard it is so hard to have an education in a digital platform way. But we need to give the credit when it is due, because of our teachers and their patience	Most of us are lacking of enthusiasm to study and finish our school activity because this is new to us for almost two years; we're always in school sharing our knowledge personally, listening to our professor in a manner that we will understand them clearly, because they are physically present, but now everything is virtual.
You have more time with your family, you can bond with them more than the usual since they are going nowhere. Most importantly, you have more time with yourself, you have more time to freshen, reflect, and improve yourself.	It's really hard to cope, and I don't have the gadget sometimes. I'm just using a mobile phone because my brothers are also students, they need to use the laptop. We have only basic even my personal stuff was borrowed by my brothers. So one of the struggles is the technology and how am I going to distribute the time and the effort that I should put.

In the third process, the identified statement indicators are categorized. Patterns were identified, and formed into themes. Below are the themes developed from the indicators. Not all indicators are used in the development of the themes. Only those indicators that are premised to answer the research questions or issues are raised in the study.

Appreciation of the school learning environment / physical interaction

- I have learned to value school more than ever before. It has given me the opportunity to realize that going to school is an opportunity, or perhaps a privilege if you will, because we have the opportunity to walk to school and talk to our classmates and teachers about how they are doing. Every day, we have the opportunity to sit in a classroom instruction and learn new and interesting topics because of our physical presence. Something I now long for.

Challenges of teachers as perceived by students

Students were able to sense the challenges of the teachers delivering remotely.

- This issue is also experienced by our teachers. This also challenged our educators to create spaces in their homes to continue teaching us despite how drastically different this is from traditional ways of teaching.
- Some teachers do not have Wi-Fi at home, so they were not able to do the things they have been doing for a long time, which is teaching.

Academic Efforts Experiences

Students described their challenges in relation to academics. What is obvious is that most of them started with a difficult stride, but later transitioned into a better remote learner. Consider these:

- During pandemic, I was enrolled for the second semester as a second-year college in Bachelor's in special needs education. Challenges came in. I was hesitant before if I will continue the whole semester. I was hesitant because I do not have internet and the lockdown was too surprising and my family was not ready.
- There were sleepless nights, which I thought was normal knowing that I do not have school classes to attend the next day. I was always in my room, locking myself inside and reorganizing my stuff and clothes. I was busy doing so many things that I should not be doing, but I still did it, yet none of my school work was done.
- Sometimes it's hard for me to assess if I am really learning or if I am just submitting work to finish a semester. Concentrating is already a challenge in the traditional school setting, but it became ten times harder because we're at home. It's hard for us to focus at home, specifically if we're in our rooms or beds, because our minds are trained to rest at home.
- My course has a lot of hands-on and laboratory trainings. Doing hands-on, practical, and laboratory activities are an issue because doing it online is not the same. It doesn't even come close.
- Distance learning has made us miss a lot of school activities, and experiences with our communities and peers. Learning in school was not just about academic activities. We also have events, organization work, and other extracurricular activities that were meant to hone us.
- The online class started, at first, I'm having difficulty to cope especially in my PE subject because it needs to be physical. It requires a video that you really did the activity. Just one subject, but I felt like I can't survive online class, how else if all of the subjects, I thought to myself.
- I started to feel stress because I don't know which/what activity I need to do first.

- I am really worried since I am already a third-year student, and schools are not operating, it is so hard for me because we have an internship and I am a little worried. The situation will ruin my dream to practice my teaching in a real classroom setting.
- There are a lot of things going through in my mind, but still I manage to do it. I message all of my professors last semester that I am sorry about my shortcomings and I will do my very best to submit all the requirements that need in that specific time that they have given me. And I am very thankful for them to understand me and my situation.
- During this pandemic, there are a lot of challenges that I experienced, but the good news is that opportunity came in. I was able to pursue my schooling, and next semester, I am already turning fourth year college student. This semester, I realized that to learn in an online classroom, as a student we must be responsible in our studies, even though it is virtual, we must be honest in all our actions. Our teachers are doing their best, for us to have a good quality education during this pandemic.
- I have encountered difficulties such as lack of learning materials, learning environment that I have, and academic stress. Lacking in learning materials is a challenge.
- I feel that most of the students this semester feels the stress that I feel because I discovered that it is more exhausting when you are just sitting and looking to a screen rather than going to school, and you have friends that can support you personally. Eventually, I have decided to enroll and take the risk I believe that I will be able to adjust and learn the online platform that we are going to use because I'm eager to learn.
- The first issue that I faced is my academic life, I am so afraid of thinking that I will not be able to finish my school year, but then again we are in the 21st century and we make things possibly happen. I finished my second year in college online, my professors are all understanding, because of our situation. There are a lot of struggles, of course, it is part of the process. Now I am currently at my third year in college, and the struggles are still there but I am getting used to it.
- The teacher cannot see the students personally, they don't know if the students fully understand the lesson, and they are not sure also if the students are honest with their answers.
- In distance learning, the main challenge is how to foster an efficient learning environment through a screen. In a classroom, we can physically see a student if they are unruly or inactive. I believe that in distance learning, assessing student's interests and behaviors in class is challenging to determine.
- Also, I feel that I do not learn from my classes, because I learn more by interacting with others. That's why I missed being in the school and I miss my classmates. So, I started to think a new way to feel motivated in studying. This pandemic is not only about having negative thoughts, feelings or experiences. I look on the bright side, I started to reflect on myself, I started to appreciate myself more because I still fighting and keep moving forward despite of the challenges I've been through. When I finished my assignments, I rewarded myself, such as I watch series to feel relax, I eat my favorite food, and I play mobile games. I organized my schedule to have a proper time management to balance my studies and answering activities or assignments, while I still help to do household chores.

Mental and Body Wellness Challenge

The experience created a challenge on the mental wellness of the students and their family. Below are some of the statements:

- Because I also suffer from this post-traumatic stress, I search about what to do when I am alone. But I suggest that this mental health is at risk, we should talk to God and give up all our anxieties

to Him and ask God for help. Asking God for help is one of the keys, why my family continues to survive on this pandemic.

- This lock down really triggered my mental health issues, my anxiety attack, my over thinking mind, and my bad break downs really an issue this lock down. I really think a lot and that is one of my bad habits.

Transforming challenges to opportunities

Their experiences also provided the ability of a person to transform the challenges to opportunities and plans for the future once the pandemic will be addressed. Below are excerpts of their statements.

- It's easy to be distracted by phones, families, and friends, so I really had to create a routine and stick with it regardless of how challenging that can be. Some of us loved going to school, the structure and building itself, because they don't have that space of learning at home. Some of us don't have their own rooms or extra areas to set up a desk and study undisturbed. Some of us don't have the electronic gadgets and tools necessary to survive the online classes.
- There were also issues about online class, like we can't contact or communicate with our professors when we have a problem to ask, or they won't communicate with us if they are not able to attend class. We are having a difficulty to communicate with each other, especially when we don't know the professor yet because it was the first time to meet her/him.
- When the semester began, I loss motivation because we don't have proper internet connection, I need to use mobile data and sometimes I connect to our neighbors Wi-Fi, but it's not enough to have a better connection because our house and their house are slightly apart, so sometimes I go outside to get close but I have another problem which is the noise made by the dogs, chickens, and the cars. I didn't hear well about the discussions and I can't focus. Also, I had difficulty studying at home because I have five little siblings, I can't stop them to play, sometimes they also fight and shout.
- One of the things that I should be thankful for during the remote class is, the opportunity for me to explore the devices that we have. When I started school, I don't even know how to create my own PowerPoint presentation. Maybe because generation wise, I was not born in a generation that technology was booming and I'm not into it. But since, we are engaged in technology nowadays, I was able to learn how to create my PowerPoint presentation, and save and manage my files in my Google Drive.

Implications of action process is the final process. The researchers examined how students make use and integrate those experiences in their future plans. Their future plans are focused on how they will use these experiences to plan their future advocacy.

The descriptive coding is again used here. Statements were categorized and patterns were identified to form themes. As educators, their advocacies are stated below:

Access to education

- My advocacy is to give every children or student a chance and access to study despite of their social status. This advocacy will not only be for academic purposes, but also to social and self-

development. I always believe that this will happen, and this will only be possible if the government will provide a fund for this and will not corrupt the money. With this advocacy, it can somehow reduce the number of children who cannot study because of poverty.

- Truly, I pity those children who are already working at a very young age, because they cannot do anything about it. If they don't work, they will starve to death. That age should not be the age for working that should be the age for playing and learning.

Models to students

- While in the middle of pandemic, I think it helps me to be a better person with stronger mindset which I can use when I became a teacher in the future. Because being a teacher is not an easy job, it requires a lot of things. So, as a teacher in the future, I advocate to always do the right thing when it comes to education so that my students will see me as a good model for them to follow.

Student's safety

- Personally, I advocate my student's safety. I think it should be the priority of the teachers to think of the safety of the students in school and even at home, especially this time of pandemic. We witnessed that many students killed themselves because of the pressure of having online class and the deadlines. As a teacher, we are the ones that students could lean on if they have problems. We can't help them solve their problems, but at least we can assure them that they have someone to talk to if they need.

Student and teacher interaction and communication

- As a teacher, we should have good communication and healthy relationship with them. Moreover, I want to advocate that students should speak about what they want, what they need and what their rights are. As a teacher, I should be their number one supporter, their guide, and the one who engage and enlighten them.

Listening and understanding person

- My plan as a teacher in this time of pandemic is to hear the students' needs and struggles in life, so that we could know how to meet their needs. It is very important to know our students, their capabilities in order for them to give the feedback that the teachers want the students to be.
- I plan to help my students with special needs. I will be sensitive to cultural differences, sensitive to varying disabilities and how they affect students and their families, honest, trustworthy, and dependable, assertive yet tactful, patient and persistence.
- As a future educator, I have come up with this advocacy as a teacher during this lockdown. I believed that teachers should be considerate in all times. Yes, we have also our own deadlines and goals to meet but let us face the truth that not all of our students are the same. Some of them are having a hard time and trying their best to give their hundred percent effort to produce quality output.

Overcoming limitations in technology

- I will suggest that in times of pandemic, internet café or computer shop should be converted into a friendly leaning environment for the students. Students will have a schedule when they can use the computer. Maybe they can have online classes two times a week, and a day for doing their assignments. Of course, there will be a facilitator to make sure that the computers are being used properly, and for the school stuffs only. Since there will be a facilitator, the students can easily ask questions regarding technical problems. Through this, students are exposed to technology in a good way, especially now that we are living in the age of technology.

Assistance from parents or significant others

- We should ask help from parents or guardians of our students. Especially most of the students are teenagers, they are prone to anxieties and maybe it may lead them to a depression. So let us ask the parents to check their children from time to time. Parents should realize that online classes could be harder than the traditional face to face classes. We should also update the parents on the status of their children in the classes, and give suggestions on how can they handle the situation effectively and in a thoughtful manner.

Discussion and Conclusion

The reflective activity clearly caused students to think about their approach, motivation, and efforts to cope with the demands of remote teaching and learning, as evidenced by the level of transparency and willingness to voice the truth of the situation in regard to challenges, issues, and concerns. As what Desautel (2009) relayed that metacognition, which enables the person to think about his or her own thinking, had a direct relationship with reflection. This increased self-awareness and direction showed that it had the potential to lead to increased intrinsic drive and execution of that motivation to its maximum capacity, resulting in new learning gains and possibly future design plans.

The reflective results of the student experiences during lockdown suggested several themes. These themes drawn from the personal experiences could be the framework to their learning gains given the challenges at hand: a) Appreciation of the school learning environment/physical interaction; b) Challenges of teachers as perceived by students; c) Academic Efforts Experiences; d) Mental and Body Wellness Challenge; e) transforming challenges to opportunities; and f) technological and home infrastructure challenge. These themes depicted the students' experiences, motivation, and learning gains during remote teaching and learning.

From another perspective, these experiences indicate their coping strategies and ways of overcoming challenges in learning, academic, technological and home infrastructure. Moreover, these experiences paved the way to think about what else can be done in times of pandemic. By reflective thinking, students were able to think what can be planned for the future career.

The second reflective question asked: Using this experience, what could be their future plans. Themes that emerged from this question are as follows: 1) access to education; 2) models to students; 3) student safety; 4) student and teacher interaction, and communication; 5) listening

and understanding person; 6) overcoming limitations in technology; and 7) assistance from significant others.

These themes emerged as future plans and advocacy can be viewed as their metacognition or their reflection-for-action. Said themes reflect on their decisional mindset or state of mind. This could serve as their mental model or framework. As stated by Cornett and Knight (2009, cited from York-Barr et al., p. 89, 2006) there are five states of mind use for guiding reflection: these are efficacy, flexibility, craftsmanship, consciousness and interdependence. The two themes could serve as the study framework. Said framework suggests that students' reflective thoughts demonstrate a mindset of both efficacy and flexibility: efficacy, which is described as having an internal locus of control knowing that you can make a difference and flexibility, which is described as thinking outside the box, and choosing to look things from a different perspective. In short, students' metacognition during remote teaching and learning has transformed the students to empower individual as one tried to make the experiences more meaningful, and to embrace those experiences to prepare for a better tomorrow.

The qualitative results of the reflective instrument clearly improved metacognition on both an intellectual and affective level, as evidenced by the majority of participants' responses to the aforementioned topics, which were either positive or negative.

These results showed the extent to which the participants practice metacognition during lockdown. While this action research has reached the limits of the power of reflection in the classroom and brought new perspectives, it appears that additional factors are needed, such as more time to fully explore the full potential of reflection as a tool for increased metacognition (Flavell, 1976, 1979).

Teachers could then build on the power of heightened metacognition by providing activities and interventions that allow students to assess their intellectual and motivational approaches to the problem, using this step as an initial point, thus propelling them toward substantial learning gains in any situation.

While the study is able to explore the positive, negative and new realizations of the students, it may not inherently translate into academic success or improvement as multifactorial hindrances remain on the landscape of every home and to every individual student. What is more important is that new perspectives are drawn from the reflective activity.

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